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Technology Adoption and Service Delivery in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State

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Abstract

The continuous effort to develop a better and more efficient way of service delivery has led to the introduction of digital technologies in the public sector; this, in turn, has transformed various parts of the modern sector, playing a pivotal role in the socio-economic growth of African nations. This has made it imperative to study the phenomenon of technology adoption on service delivery in Nigerian tertiary institutions. The objective of this study is to examine the effects and challenges of technology adoption on service delivery at Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State. The study employs an exploratory and descriptive research design, utilising both primary and secondary data. Using Institutional theory, it argues that an organisation adopts certain structures and practices to gain legitimacy. From a total population of 953, which comprised both the administrative staff (446) and academic staff (507) of the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State, a sample size of 281 was drawn using Taro Yamane's formula at a 5% level of significance. The study discovered that digital technologies have streamlined administrative processes, workflow, and this has led to staff efficiency. The study also revealed that digital systems have improved communication between the students and the staff in the institution. The study recommended that the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro should introduce digital innovation training through external exposures, qualitative workshop and seminar to equip staff on the uses of digital tools. It is concluded among others, the need to address the challenges of resistance to change among staff, cyber security and privacy risk so as to embrace the new development to foster the mindset that prioritize efficiency, timeliness and quality service delivery in Nigeria tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Digital Tools, E- learning, Online Registration, Public Service Delivery

Introduction

The primary purpose of tertiary institutions within the public sector is to deliver high-quality education, research, and community services that meet the needs of students and society as a whole. Similar to governments worldwide, tertiary institutions have continually endeavoured to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of their service delivery through various reforms. The advent of digital technologies has significantly transformed how these institutions operate, enabling more accessible, efficient, and innovative service provision. In African nations, the digital revolution is particularly influential in advancing educational access, improving administrative processes, and fostering societal growth, thereby reinforcing the vital role of tertiary institutions in national development.

Tertiary institutions offer a range of services aligned with their goals and objectives (Ogunode & Zalakro, 2023). Fulfilling the mandates for which tertiary institutions are established makes the utilisation of human, material and technological resources a critical concern (Abid et al., 2022; Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022). In the context of public or state-owned tertiary institutions, a key expectation is the provision of efficient and high-quality services (OECD, 2024). When services offered by public organisations are effective and efficient, the objectives of such organisations are partly met, as people who receive the services derive satisfaction (Victor & Steven, 2020). Given this, in the pursuit of the key mandates of teaching, learning, research, innovations, skill acquisition and development. Tertiary educational institutions are focusing on delivering effective administrative services with cost efficiency and reduced resources (Ekere, 2019; De Lara & Santos, 2024).

Governments around the world are increasingly implementing digital transformation initiatives to enhance operational efficiency, improve service delivery, and increase citizen participation. To boost efficiency, responsiveness and openness in the public sector, digital transformation requires rethinking administrative procedures and incorporating cutting-edge technologies (UN, 2020). The increased prevalence of digital transformation in the public sector has inspired a growing interest among academics and policymakers in examining its effects and repercussions. Numerous studies have investigated the advantages and disadvantages of digital government efforts, emphasising how they can increase citizen satisfaction, governance, and the quality of public services (Heeks, 2018; UN E-Government Survey, 2022).

Governments prioritize digital transformation because it can lead to openness, faster and simpler access to services, less corruption and improved public sector performance. Porrura et al. (2021) posited that digital transformation is a movement in organisational procedures and institutional culture that uses information and communication technologies (ICTs) to address the demands of businesses and citizens in a safe, free, and effective manner. According to Aker (2017), digital technology can enhance people's access to public information, facilitate data collection for the more efficient distribution of public goods, and widen access to financial services via mobile money in the provision of public services. The availability of digital technology has created significant opportunities for public service to enhance service provision, transparency, and citizen trust in the system (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2021). Though public service delivery is crucial in every country as these organizations are established to carry out certain tasks like regulatory functions, enhancing government mandate execution, cutting down on bureaucracy in service delivery, increasing efficiency in delivering services and focusing on government interests (Chepkonga, Nzioki, & Kiprop, 2018) but the impact of digital technologies in recent times cannot be over emphasized.

Technology adoption in the educational sector combines an educational institution's data and functions into a unified single system. This connection improves functionality, making it more efficient, organised and accurate. These platforms are designed to be simple to use, saving money and time while providing the flexibility needed to respond to changes in the educational landscape. While educational institutions must deal with a variety of demands,

including registration, admissions, student records, class scheduling, transportation, attendance tracking, library operations, financial oversight, exams, performance monitoring, grading, hostel administration, security and report generation. Software vendors usually offer a range of modules, allowing schools to select the ones that best meet their specific needs.

Statement of the Problem

Academic service delivery has improved dramatically as a result of the advancement of digital technologies. The digital transformation programmes aim to improve the efficacy, efficiency, and accessibility of government services by improving web portals and mobile applications. This will improve citizens' access to information and services. However, it was discovered that disparities in digital literacy rates, internet access, infrastructure availability, delays, lack of transparency in service delivery, limited technology access, and resistance to change have all impacted the quality and timing of public services in Nigeria.

There is a deluge of literature on digital transformation, the majority of which is academic discussions and remains theoretical (Jha & Singh, 2021; Obidike & Onuora, 2025). Again, many higher institutions have yet to fully integrate digitalisation into their administrative routines, resulting in antiquated record-keeping and slow administrative procedures. As student enrollment grows, this issue becomes more pressing, making technological adoption even more critical for these institutions to properly meet their burgeoning demands. This research aims to address this gap by beaming its searchlight on the effect of Technology Adoption in public service delivery: a study of Nigerian tertiary institutions, Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State in particular.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the effects of Technology Adoption on academic service delivery in Nigeria. The following consists of the specific objectives formulated for this study:

- i.** To ascertain the effects of Technology Adoption on Administrative and Academic service delivery in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State.
- ii.** To examine the Challenges of Technology Adoption in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State.

Literature Review

Digital Transformation

Digital transformation refers to both technology breakthroughs and their integration into the larger social structure. This integration encompasses all aspects of the technical environment and has a substantial impact on societal factors, diverging from previous notions of digitalisation in public administration (Sanina et al., 2023).

According to Ashfaq (2023), digital transformation in the government and public sector is a complex process that involves strategically integrating technology and digital advancements. This approach aims to revitalise public service delivery by using digital solutions, which necessitates not just improved tools but also a fundamental rethinking of operating procedures.

Government agencies aim to achieve two major objectives through digital transformation: enhancing service delivery and refining internal operations.

Group engagement and collaborative information behaviours that foster an information culture in digital channels of communication are the foundation of digital transformation readiness. These behaviours may have an impact on effective information management and information use throughout the organisation's rapid digital transformation (Deja, Rak, & Bell, 2021).

Digital Technology

Defining technology adoption is necessary, according to (Zulham et al., 2023), who also examine it from two different angles. From the perspective of a worker, they are concerned about their positions being taken over by advancements in technology. Previously, many believed that technology would eventually replace human jobs, leading to a pessimistic view that the main goal of technology was to eliminate the need for human labour. On the contrary, there are individuals who argue that the presence of technology elevates humans to a superior status, making life more convenient and comfortable. Furthermore, digital technology improves companies' capacity to share and restructure knowledge, as well as incorporate diverse external knowledge with an open mindset (Wang & Du, 2021). It also enables the internal reorganisation of knowledge through the analysis and organisation of large amounts of data, facilitating a shift from knowledge discovery to value creation and informed management decisions (Liu et al., 2020).

For the purpose of this study, digital technology refers to tools and systems that facilitate knowledge sharing, data analysis, and organisational restructuring.

Academic Service Delivery

The successful transformation of academic service delivery in tertiary institutions depends on institutions with well-defined policies, competent personnel, visionary leadership, and actively engaged stakeholders, including students, faculty, and administrators. Higher education institutions can strengthen trust and credibility by offering innovative and transparent approaches to teaching, research, and administration through the adoption of relevant digital technologies (Milakovich, 2022).

Academic Service Delivery (DASD) can be described as the application of digital technologies to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of designing, processing, and delivering academic and administrative services to students, staff, and other stakeholders (Adeola et al., 2022). This encompasses a broad range of services, including e-learning platforms, online registration systems, digital libraries, research management, student support services, and virtual communication channels. Through these innovations, tertiary institutions provide essential academic services that support teaching, learning, research, and community engagement, thereby contributing to national development.

For the purpose of this study, academic service delivery is seen as a tool and platforms such as e-learning systems, online registration systems, digital libraries, research management

tools, and virtual communication channels. These digital technologies are adopted to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of academic and administrative services in tertiary institutions.

4.0 Empirical Review

Obidike and Onuora (2025) investigate the effect of digital transformation on public sector accountability and transparency in Nigeria. The study was grounded in institutional theory, and a survey design was employed to collect data through a questionnaire. The study findings revealed that the adoption of IPPIS and TSA has a positive and significant effect on transparency and accountability in Federal government MDAs in Nigeria at a 5% level of significance. The study concluded that the adoption of IPPIS and TSA has reduced financial irregularities and also ensured transparency in the Nigerian public sector. It was recommended that the government should enforce the adoption of IPPIS and make it mandatory for all MDAs and agencies to adhere to it, as its adoption has significantly ensured transparency in the MDAs.

Yusuf and Ruthwunnie (2024) evaluate the relationship between digitalisation and public service delivery in public universities. The study employed a case study approach involving 61946 students, 10 departments and 5 digital department officers, selecting 227 individuals as respondents. Data were gathered through a questionnaire. The findings show a moderate positive correlation between the quality of resources and service delivery in Puntland's public universities, with a correlation coefficient of 0.476 ($p < 0.05$). It was recommended that the scope of digitalisation should be broadened to enhance service delivery and tackle digitalisation challenges.

Ibrahim (2025) investigate empowering higher education through digital transformation and strategies planning for academic advancement. Structural equation modeling was used as the primary methodology. The dataset consist of 224 participants and 15 indicators. The result shows that a two tailed test with $t=-1.96$ at a 95% significance level found automation significantly affects strategic planning ($B=0.36$, $t=2.97$, $p=0.000$), and digitalization significantly affects strategic planning ($B=0.30$, $t=2.68$, $p=0.01$). By integrating digitalization into their strategic planning, organizations can create a robust digital infrastructure that improves data capabilities, encourages innovation, and boosts agility, providing a sense of security about the future of Omani higher education.

Jimoh and Jimoh (2024) explore the influence of digital technology on administrative service delivery in tertiary institutions. Survey design method was adopted for the study, the population comprises of an administrative staff of the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State. The result shows high digital technology use for administrative functions and that it contributes significantly to rate of administrative service delivery. It was also discovered that digital technology facilitates administrative workflow and enhances the rate and quality of administrative services to a wide range of stakeholders, including students, alumni, external organisations, etc. The study recommends, among others, that the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro and other similar institutions should intensify their digital transformation drive in the form of resources, platforms, etc., with a view to providing satisfactory administrative services.

Gondo and Suwaryono (2024) examined the impact of digital transformation on public service delivery in Zimbabwe. The study employed quantitative methods with stratified random techniques. The study found that the adoption of digital transformation in Zimbabwe

has streamlined processes, improved resource utilisation and enhanced responsiveness to citizens' inquiries and feedback.

Hong (2025) examined the role of digital transformation of higher education institutions in economic competitiveness. The study took 291 prefecture-level cities in China as the research area. The study found that the regression coefficient between the digital transformation of colleges and universities and regional economic competitiveness is greater than 0 and passes the 1% significance level test, indicating that digital transformation in colleges and universities can significantly enhance regional economic competitiveness.

Ndaba and Naidoo (2024) examine digital transformation challenges in higher education institutions post covid-19. The study adopted descriptive research design and non-probability sampling methods. The study collected data from 177 support staff members across various departments. The study findings indicate that employees' digital skills need improvement.

Theoretical Framework

Selznick (1957) introduced the Institutional Theory, which Scout (2001) further developed, explaining how institutional surroundings impact organisations and how they adhere to institutional norms, regulations, and values.

The theory assumes that organisations conform to the demands and expectations of their institutional context by applying specific structures and practices to obtain legitimacy, efficiency, stability, effectiveness, and resources. Institutional theory examines how public sector enterprises adopt digital tools in response to demands from regulatory bodies, public expectations, and technological advancements. For example, the public's need for more effective and efficient service delivery, as well as government laws, drive the public sector to use digital technology.

The idea contributes to understanding how good service delivery and digital transformation are tied to prevailing norms and values. It investigates how these digital advances are implemented into the current operations of public sector organisations, as well as whether they adhere to or violate established standards. Institutional theory explains how businesses respond to the digital revolution. It investigates how new digital practices are integrated into public-sector organisations and how they alter organisational structures and routines.

However, the theory is being criticised for contextual limitation; the theory assumes a uniformity of institutional pressures across contexts, but in reality, pressures vary significantly by region, culture, and sector. In African tertiary institutions, for example, resource constraints, infrastructural deficits, and varying levels of digital literacy complicate the straightforward adoption of institutional norms promoted in developed contexts.

This theory is relevant to this study because it offers a framework for understanding how pressures from institutional bodies, such as regulatory bodies, public expectations, and technological advancements, influence the adoption of digital technologies. The theory also demonstrates the impact of technology adoption on academic service delivery.

Conceptual Framework

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE

TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION

- Online registration
- E-learning
- E-library
- E-Payment

DEPENDENT VARIABLE

SERVICE DELIVERY

- Improved Efficiency
- Increased accessibility and transparency
- Improved Satisfaction
- Reduced Complaints
- Improved record keeping
- Improved communication
- Increased performance tracking of students

Source: Maroa and Namusonge (2024)
Researcher (2025)

Methodology

This study employs descriptive survey design. This design was chosen because it can be used to elicit information from the respondents on the topic under investigation. Simple random techniques was chosen to select the participants for this study. The population for this study are staff of Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State. From a total population of 953 which comprised both the administrative staff (446) and academic staff (507) of the institutions, a sample size of 281 was drawn using Taro Yamane's formula at 5% level of significance.

Data were collected through a primary method, where a structured questionnaire was used to elicit detailed information from respondents on the effect of digital transformation on administrative and academic service delivery. The questionnaire utilised 4 4-point Likert scale, ranked from strongly agree(1), agree (2), strongly disagree (3), and disagree (4), to guide the respondents' levels of agreement.

Through the quantitative method, the study employed a simple percentage and frequency distribution table to summarise the information generated from the field. The formulated hypotheses were tested using multiple regression statistics at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Interpretation

This section presents the frequency and percentage tables, which provide an analysis of the responses gathered from the respondents in relation to achieving the study's objectives. Of the 281 questionnaires administered, 240 were completed and returned, which were used for data analysis. For the purpose of this study, all analyses were conducted using SPSS Version 25. The hypothesis was tested with regression analysis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Effects of Technology Adoption on Administrative and Academic Service Delivery in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State

Variables	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Technology Adoption has improved efficiency of administrative processes in my institution	75(34.1)	126(57.3)	4(1.8)	15(6.8)
The uses of digital tools has improved recording keeping, registration and fee payment	96(43.6)	83(37.7)	38(17.3)	3(1.4)
Digital tools has enhanced the delivery of academic content through the uses of e-learning	72(32.7)	104(47.3)	26(11.8)	18(8.2)
The uses of digital system has improved communication between the student and the staff	84(38.2)	86(39.1)	35(15.9)	15(6.8)
Technology Adoption has help in reducing complaint	101(45.9)	56(25.5)	45(20.9)	17(7.7)
The use of digital tools has help in increasing accessibility and transparency	70(31.8)	85(38.6)	40 (18.2)	25(11.4)

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 2: Challenges of Technology Adoption in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro Ogun State

Variables	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Limited financial resources affect effective implementation of Technology Adoption in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro	104(47.3)	98(44.5)	11(5.0)	7(3.2)
Resistance to change among public servants hindered effective implementation of Technology Adoption	63(28.6)	114(51.8)	37(16.8)	6(2.7)
Infrastructural constraint affects effective implementation of Technology Adoption	89(40.5)	87(39.5)	33(15.0)	11(5.0)
Concerns over cybersecurity and privacy risk hindered effective implementation of Technology Adoption in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro	77(35.0)	82(37.3)	42(19.1)	19(8.6)

Lack of adequate staff training on uses of digital tools affect effective implementation of Technology Adoption in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro

96(43.6)

83(37.7)

23(10.5)

18(8.2)

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 3: Hypothesis Testing

Variable	Coefficient	T-stat	P-value
Constant	5.691	9.316	.000
Public service delivery (PSD)	.480	6.080	.000
Adjusted R Squared	.141		
F-stat	36.961		
Sig	.000 ^b		

a. Dependent Variable: Public service delivery

b. Predictors: (Constant), technology adoption

Relationship between Technology Adoption and Public Service Delivery

This section determines extent to which technology adoption and public service delivery are related. The null hypothesis assumed that there is no significant relationship between technology adoption and public service delivery. Simple linear regression analysis (using SPSS 25) was conducted to determine the effects of independent variables on dependent variables. In Table 3, the results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between technology adoption and public service delivery (coefficient = 0.480, p-value = 0.000). Overall, the F-ratio indicates that the independent variables statistically significantly predict the dependent variable, $F = 36.961, p < 0.000$.

Decision: The p-value of the research outcome is 0.000, which is less than the 0.05% level of significance. This means that technology adoption is statistically significant with public service delivery. This denoted that we reject the null hypothesis and concluded that technology adoption has a significant effect on public service delivery.

Discussion of Findings

The first objective of the study was to examine the effect of technology adoption on administrative and academic service delivery at the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State. The aim of this objective was to investigate how the adoption of digital tools in the institution has influenced the productivity, effectiveness, and transparency of staff in service delivery. The first statement illustrated that 57.3% of the total respondents indicated that digital transformation has improved the effectiveness of administrative processes in the institution. The result suggested that digital technologies have streamlined administrative processes and workflow which has led to staff effectiveness. It was also discovered that uses of digital tools

has improved recording keeping, registration and fee payment in the institution with 43.6% of the respondents attested. This implied that digital technologies have ensured faster service delivery by making staff more effective and reducing errors.

Also, 47.3% of the respondents claimed that digital tools has enhanced the delivery of academic content through the uses of e-learning. The suggested that digital technology has enabled flexible and accessible learning experiences, allowing students and lecturers to access learning materials remotely at their convenience, this potentially increased students engagement and outcomes. Additionally, 39.1% of the respondents agreed that uses of digital system have improved communication between the student and the staff. This indicated that digital platforms such as email and learning messaging system have improved the ability of both academic and administrative staff to respond to student needs faster and has led to a more collaborative environment.

On the ground that technology adoption has help in reducing complaint, the result showed the response that represented 45.9% of the total respondents. Thus, the implications of this finding showed that digital technology has helped in addressing issues promptly, reducing grievances and improving overall satisfaction. Also, 38.6% respondents stated that use of digital tools has help in increasing accessibility and transparency. This suggests that digital technologies have made information more accessible to the staff and students. However, these findings are not surprising as it is in line with the study of Tinashe, Suwaryono (2024) and Jimoh & Jimoh (2024). The study explored the influence of digital technology on administrative service delivery in tertiary institutions. The study discovered that digital technology is widely used for administrative tasks and that it has a major impact on the rate at which administrative services are provided.

The second objective investigates the challenges of digital transformation in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro. On the notion that limited resources affect effective utilization of digital transformation, 47.3% of the respondents stated that many institutions in Nigeria struggle with limited budget making it challenging to provide comprehensive equipment and tools needed for effective utilization of digital transformation. 51.8% of the respondent stated that one of the major challenges facing digital transformation in the institution is inability of the staff especially among administrative staff to adapt to new development (technology). This is as a result of employees been comfortable with traditional method of operation.

Additionally, infrastructural constraint was stated as another challenge obstruct digital transformation in the institution. This can be attributed to the country's unstable power supply and network barriers. Again, there was a cybersecurity and privacy risk; 37.3% of the respondents attested that cybersecurity can compromise student data and also obstruct the effectiveness of the institution's portal. Additionally, 43.6% of the respondents stated that inadequate training on the use of digital tools hinders the effective implementation of digital transformation within the institution. This resulted in a skill gap, where employees lack the necessary competencies to utilise digital tools to perform to their full potential. However, these findings are not surprising, as they align with the study by Ugochukwu, Okeoma, Samuel, and Abel (2024), which examined digital transformation in public sector services. The research found that obstacles, such as reluctance to change, cybersecurity threats, and the need for ongoing training, need to be addressed to maximise the benefits of digital transformation.

Conclusion

This study examined the effect of Technology Adoption on academic service delivery in Nigerian tertiary institutions. The study specifically focused on administrative and academic service delivery cum the challenges facing digital transformation in the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State. The findings indicated that digital transformation has led to improvements in areas such as student and staff registration, record-keeping, fee payment, effective communication among staff and students, increased efficiency, and transparency, among others. However, in order to enhance the efficiency of digitalisation utilisation in the institution, the study emphasised the need to address the challenges of resistance to change among staff, cybersecurity and privacy risk, among others and should embrace the new development to engender a mindset that prioritises efficiency, timeliness and quality service delivery in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Based on the findings, it is concluded that the implementation of digital transformation at Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State, has significantly contributed to the development of both academic and administrative staff within the institution, thereby enhancing service delivery. In addition, the study further concluded that the adoption of digital technology is not just a trend but a necessity that must be implemented to improve service delivery in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

- The Federal Polytechnic Ilaro should introduce digital innovation training through exposures, qualitative workshop and seminar to equip the staff on the uses of digital tools
- The government should provide adequate funds and assistance to tertiary education to ensure efficient utilization of digital technology
- The management of the Institution should encourage staff to update their skills, knowledge on digital tools and application in order to be efficient and relevant in today's world cum rendering services to the students, other institution, stakeholders etc.

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